

Coumaryl 6-isoCyanate and its Reactions.

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The action of an excess of carbonyl chloride on 6-aminocoumarin in cold dry benzene solution results in the formation of a mixture of coumaryl 6-isocyanate and aminocoumarin hydrochloride, the reaction being supposed to take place through the intermediate carbamyl chloride, thus:

If, however, the aminocoumarin employed be in excess, the reaction proceeds further and an almost theoretical yield of pure symmetrical dicoumarylcarbamide is obtained.

Coumaryl 6-isocyanate is a crystalline solid dissolving readily in benzene and other solvents, and although it resembles phenyl isocyanate in most of its reactions; it is found to be relatively stabler and less reactive than the latter. When kept in contact with water it changes only slowly into dicoumarylcarbamide. The condensation with alcohols, phenols and amines is best carried out by warming on the water-bath, the resulting ethyl coumarylcarbamate and coumarylcarbamides being usually mixed with a small amount of symmetrical dicoumarylcarbamide which is formed as a by-product. The latter is practically insoluble in boiling alcohol and is therefore easily separated from the main products of the reaction. Symmetrical dicoumarylcarbamide has also been obtained in an excellent yield by heating aminocoumarin and carbamide in glacial acetic acid solution (*cf.* Sonn, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 2440).

It is interesting to note that monocoumarylcarbamide and phenylcoumarylcarbamide, which were prepared by reacting aminocoumarin with potassium cyanate and phenyl isocyanate respectively, were found to be identical with those derived from the condensation

In the present case, however, the hydrolysis obviously proceeds normally, not a trace of the insoluble dicoumarylcarbamide being isolated, thus:

The reaction of ethyl coumaryl-6-carbamate with aniline is interesting. No reaction is observed below 150°, but when the temperature is raised to 200°, and a molecular equivalent of aniline is employed, a mixture of diphenyl- and dicoumaryl-carbamides is formed. If, however, an excess of aniline (4 mols.) be used and the temperature maintained at 180-190° a mixture of diphenylcarbamide and 6-aminocoumarin is found to be produced to the complete exclusion of dicoumarylcarbamide. These observations may be explained by assuming the formation, in the first instance, of phenylcoumarylcarbamide which decomposed in the vicinity of its melting point (220°) in the manner indicated before. In the presence of a large excess of aniline and at a lower temperature, the influence of mass becomes prominent and the aniline simply displaces the aminocoumarin from its combination. The changes may be represented by the following equations:

4: 7-Dimethylcoumaryl 6-*isocyanate*, which has been prepared in a similar manner, and some of its derivatives are also described here.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Coumaryl 6-isoCyanate, $\text{C}_9\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\cdot\text{NCO}$.—6-Aminocoumarin (2 g.) suspended in a fine state in dry benzene (30 c.c.), was added slowly

with stirring to a solution of carbonyl chloride in toluene (20 per cent.) which was cooled in ice. A white cloudy precipitate was formed. After standing overnight at the laboratory temperature, the mixture was filtered, the residue extracted with cold benzene, and the combined filtrate concentrated. Colourless glistening prismatic needles of the isocyanate were deposited, melting at 163° ; the pure product weighed 0.5 g. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 2.9; N, 7.5. $C_{10}H_5O_3N$ requires C, 64.2; H, 2.7; N, 7.5 per cent.).

The residue insoluble in benzene dissolved almost completely on treatment with hot water leaving a small portion which was found to be dicoumarylcarbamide (m.p. 326° , decomp.). The filtrate, on rendering alkaline, yielded yellow crystals of 6-aminocoumarin weighing 1.2 g.

Coumaryl 6-isocyanate can be preserved unchanged in well-oppered bottles. It is stable in dry air, but in moist atmosphere it slowly changes into dicoumarylcarbamide. Warm water rapidly hydrolyses it producing dicoumarylcarbamide and carbon dioxide.

Ethyl Coumaryl-6-carbamate (6-Coumarylurethane), $C_9H_5O_2 \cdot NH \cdot CO_2Et$.—This was prepared in two different ways: (a) Coumaryl isocyanate was boiled with excess of absolute alcohol and the solution filtered and concentrated. The urethane separated in colourless rectangular plates melting at 156° . The small residue insoluble in alcohol was identified with dicoumarylcarbamide. (b) 6-Aminocoumarin (2 g.) was treated with 25 c.c. of *N*-sodium carbonate solution, warmed to 60° , and ethyl chlorocarbonate (2.2 c.c.) slowly added with vigorous stirring. The straw-coloured, flocculent precipitate was filtered off, and crystallised from dilute alcohol, using animal charcoal, colourless rectangular plates being obtained (m.p. 156°) (yield 2.4 g.). (Found: C, 61.6; H, 4.8; N, 6.2. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 61.8; H, 4.7; N, 6.0 per cent.).

The coumarylurethane dissolves readily in alcohol, acetic acid, benzene and other common organic solvents. On heating for an hour to a temperature of 200° to 250° , symmetrical dicoumarylcarbamide was formed. The substance first melted and subsequently solidified to a light brown mass. The product was ground in a mortar, boiled repeatedly with alcohol, and the residue crystallised from nitrobenzene which deposited colourless crystals of the dicoumarylcarbamide (m.p. 326°).

The urethane was unaffected by boiling water, but on heating with water in a sealed tube at 180° — 200° for three hours, a clear

solution was obtained from which, on cooling, crystals of aminocoumarin (m.p. 165°) separated out. Similarly, although boiling concentrated hydrochloric acid failed to decompose the compound, it was quickly hydrolysed on heating with the acid in a sealed tube at 120°. The clear solution, on making alkaline with ammonia, precipitated yellow crystals of aminocoumarin.

Action of Aniline on Coumarylurethane.—No action occurred below 150°, the original substances being recovered unchanged at the end of three hours' heating. On using a little over a molecular proportion of aniline and maintaining the temperature at 200-220° for two hours, a dark mass was obtained from which, after repeatedly washing with hot alcohol and crystallising the residue from nitrobenzene, colourless crystals of dicoumarylcarbamide (m.p. 326°) were finally produced.

When a large excess of aniline (4 mols.) was employed and the temperature kept at 180-190°, a gray pasty mass was produced which after washing with dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallising twice from boiling alcohol using animal charcoal, formed sharp colourless needles melting at 236°. A mixed melting point determination with a pure sample of diphenylcarbamide showed them to be identical.

When equimolecular quantities of ethyl coumaryl-6-carbamate and 6-aminocoumarin were heated together at 200-220° for an hour and the product purified in the usual manner, crystals of dicoumarylcarbamide alone were obtained.

Besides the ethyl ester the following three alkyl coumarylcarbamates have been prepared by (a) condensing coumaryl 6-isocyanate with the corresponding alcohol, and by (b) reacting 6-aminocoumarin with the corresponding chlorocarbonic ester:

Methyl Coumaryl-6-carbamate, m.p. 200-201°.

Propyl Coumaryl-6-carbamate, m.p. 129-130°.

isoButyl cupsoumaryl 6-carbamate, m.p. 155-156°.

Phenyl Coumaryl-6-carbamate, $C_9H_5O_2 \cdot NH \cdot CO_2Ph$.—Coumaryl isocyanate was boiled with a slight excess of phenol in dry benzene for an hour. The benzene was distilled off, and the residue washed with weak alcohol to remove unchanged phenol. Crystallisation from hot alcohol gave colourless plates melting at 186.7°. (Found: N, 5.29. $C_{16}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 5.3 per cent.)

Symmetrical 6-dicoumarylcarbamide, $(C_9H_5O_5 \cdot NH)_2CO$.—This has been prepared by the following methods:—

(a) A solution of 6-aminocoumarin (1 mol.) and coumaryl 6-isocyanate (1 mol.) in dry benzene is boiled for a few minutes. The bulky precipitate is filtered, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and with alcohol and finally crystallised from hot nitrobenzene.

(b) Carbonyl chloride (1 mol.) was mixed with 6-aminocoumarin (4 mols.) in benzene solution, the mixture allowed to remain at the ordinary temperature for an hour and finally boiled for half an hour. The precipitate consisting of a mixture of dicoumarylcarbamide and aminocoumarin hydrochloride was filtered, washed with boiling water and the residue dried and crystallised from nitrobenzene (m.p. 325°).

(c) Carbamide (1 mol.) and 6-aminocoumarin (2 mols.) were mixed with sufficient glacial acetic acid to form a clear solution, and the acid boiled off from a sand-bath till the whole turned into a viscous mass. This was collected, washed and crystallised in the usual way. (Found: N, 8.34. $C_{19}H_{12}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.04 per cent.).

Coumaryl-6-carbamide, $C_9H_5O_2 \cdot NH \cdot CO \cdot NH_2$.—It was prepared by the following methods:

(a) A current of dry ammonia was passed through a solution of coumaryl 6-isocyanate in dry benzene and the reaction completed by allowing to stand for an hour. The bulky gelatinous precipitate was filtered and crystallised from alcohol; needles melting at 245° .

(b) 6-Aminocoumarin hydrochloride was dissolved in cold water, and the solution treated gradually with a slight excess of potassium cyanate. The precipitate was crystallised from hot glacial acetic acid which deposited colourless needles melting at 245° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.8. $C_{10}H_8O_3N_2$ requires N, 13.72 per cent.).

The monocoumarylcarbamide solidified after melting, the product being found to be pure dicoumarylcarbamide.

Sym.-6-coumarylphenylcarbamide, $C_9H_5O_2 \cdot NH \cdot CO \cdot NHPh$.—This was readily obtained as a crystalline precipitate on boiling a mixture of either coumaryl isocyanate and aniline, or phenyl isocyanate and aminocoumarin in dry benzene for a few minutes. Crystallisation from boiling alcohol gave colourless needles melting at $225-226^\circ$, with decomposition. (Found: N, 10.1. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.0 per cent.).

Coumarylphenylcarbamide (1 g.) was heated in a tube at $220^\circ-240^\circ$ for an hour; the solid melted, darkened in colour and then

solidified again. At the same time, colourless needles were found to have sublimed to the top of the tube which melted at 236° , and were identified as those of diphenylcarbamide. The dark residue at the bottom of the tube, after washing and crystallising from nitrobenzene, melted at 325° , and was proved to be dicoumarylcarbamide.

Phenyl-6-coumarylsemicarbazide, $\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_9\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$.—Coumaryl isocyanate in dry benzene solution was treated with phenylhydrazine and then boiled for an hour. The separating solid was crystallised from boiling alcohol which deposited the semicarbazide as slender colourless needles melting at 236° . (Found: N, 14.48. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires N, 14.23 per cent.).

Condensation of Coumaryl isoCyanate and Acetoxime: Formation of $\text{C}_9\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}_2\cdot\text{N}:\text{C}(\text{Me})_2$.—Equivalent amounts of the isocyanate and the oxime were boiled in benzene for an hour; the product crystallised on cooling as colourless hexagonal tablets melting at 187° . (Found: N, 10.89. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires N, 10.77 per cent.).

4:7-Dimethylcoumaryl 6-isoCyanate.—This was prepared from 4:7-dimethyl-6-aminocoumarin by the action of carbonyl chloride in the usual way. It crystallised from benzene as colourless stout needles melting at 215° . (Found: N, 6.86. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 6.51 per cent.).

Ethyl 4:7-Dimethylcoumaryl-6-carbamate, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C}_9\text{H}_3\text{O}_2\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$.—This was obtained in two ways, viz., (a) by boiling the isocyanate with absolute alcohol, and (b) by treating a suspension of the aminocoumarin in warm sodium carbonate solution with ethyl chlorocarbonate. It separated from hot alcohol as colourless flat needles melting at 196° . (Found: N, 5.49. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires N, 5.36 per cent.).

4:7-Dimethylcoumaryl-6-carbamide, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\cdot\text{C}_9\text{H}_3\text{O}_2\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}_2$.—The gelatinous precipitate which came down on passing dry ammonia through a benzene solution of the isocyanate was collected, washed with alcohol and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. Colourless prisms were obtained melting at 250° (decomp.). The new product formed after decomposition melted at $328\text{--}330^{\circ}$, and was identified as di-4:7-dimethylcoumarylcarbamide. (Found: N, 12.37. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires N, 12.07 per cent.).

Phenyl-4:7-dimethylcoumaryl-6-carbamide, $\text{Me}_2\text{C}_9\text{H}_3\text{O}_2\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{Ph}$.—The same product was obtained by condensing either (a) 4:7-dimethylcoumaryl 6-isocyanate with aniline, or (b) 6-amino-

4:7-dimethylcoumarin with phenyl isocyanate. It formed needles from benzene melting at 265-266° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.5. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.1 per cent.).

Di-(4:7-dimethyl)-6-coumarylcarbamide, $[Me_2C_9H_3O_2 \cdot NH]_2CO$.—This was prepared by all the three different methods described in connection with dicoumarylcarbamide. It crystallised from nitrobenzene in colourless prisms melting at 320-330°. (Found: N, 7.2. $C_{23}H_{20}O_5N_2$ requires N, 6.93 per cent.).

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